

THE IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPING ECONOMIC LITERACY IN FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS AND THE INFLUENCING FACTORS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the importance of developing economic literacy among students by primary school teachers, as well as the factors influencing economic literacy and its components. Additionally, strategies for improving economic education are presented.*

Keywords: *Economic literacy, education, economic consciousness, economic knowledge, economic skills.*

The rapidly developing economic and sociological conditions are increasing the importance of economic literacy, as making economic decisions today is a much more complex and risk-based process compared to the past. Economic literacy is essential because it simplifies understanding of the world and economic system, helps individuals make informed decisions, and encourages them to be more rational. One of the primary functions of economic literacy is to develop economic knowledge and skills, enabling individuals to collaborate effectively with others.

Although economic literacy helps people make sound economic decisions, it should not be seen as a universal solution to all economic problems. Lusardi and Tufano [6] found that individuals with low financial literacy are more likely to take on high-cost debt and face financial difficulties. Academic literature supports the significance of economic education in schools [9].

In the United States, since 1985, high school students have been taught economics courses covering the basics of microeconomic and macroeconomic analysis [4]. Additionally, the standardized Test of Economic Literacy (TEL) is used to measure U.S. high school students' understanding of economics and to monitor the effectiveness of this education [11].

The key components of economic literacy include economic knowledge, behavior, skills, and competence. "These encompass the knowledge, abilities, and behaviors necessary for individuals to make successful decisions in economic life and improve their financial well-being" [12].

Economic knowledge – refers to understanding the fundamental principles and concepts of economics. For elementary school students, this involves learning basic concepts such as money, production, and trade. For example, children can develop economic knowledge by answering questions like "Why do we need money?"

Economic behavior – describes the habits individuals display in various economic situations. For students, this includes developing habits such as saving, planning, and making responsible purchases.

Economic skills – are practical abilities applied in different economic scenarios. For students, this involves simple skills such as budgeting and planning purchases.

Economic competence – is the ability to apply economic knowledge, behavior, and skills in real life. For students, this means spending money wisely, planning, and making responsible

decisions. For example, if a child wants to buy a book with their own money, they might have to save for several weeks before making the purchase. This demonstrates their competence—not only in saving money but also in practicing patience.

Figure 1. Indicators of Economic Literacy Development.

Developing a national economic education program is a fundamental starting point, without which it would be difficult to achieve a high level of economic literacy among both the general population and young people.

Research has shown that numerous factors influence economic literacy. Gerek and Kurt [3] identified four key sub-factors: economic knowledge, economic rationality, socio-economic reflection, and personal economic planning. Merve [7] emphasizes that human capital, economic education, workforce training, experience, age, income and investment, gender, and race are factors affecting economic literacy (Figure 2).

Education: As mentioned earlier, education is one of the key factors influencing economic literacy. According to Japelli, there is a positive correlation between an individual's knowledge and skills and their level of economic literacy [5]. The economic knowledge level of a teacher is directly related to economic literacy [10].

Figure 2. Factors Influencing the Level of Economic Literacy.

- Confidence in the Benefits of Economic Literacy: If people believe that economic literacy helps them earn money, they will be more willing to learn about it. In general, adults understand that economic literacy can help them make a profit. Therefore, age and experience influence the level of economic literacy. Chen and Volpe found that individuals under the age of 30 with little work experience scored lower on tests [2].

- Interest in Economics: Some individuals may have a greater interest in specific fields of study. Often, men tend to be more interested in economics, football, and other related topics.

- Care should be taken when presenting materials in any subject within the elementary school curriculum to ensure that young children do not face difficulties. This is especially important for economic education.

- "Just as reading and writing enable people to lead an effective life, understanding economic concepts through economic literacy provides individuals with the necessary skills to make informed decisions. Changes in modern society give people more responsibility and power in making financial decisions while making consumer economic opportunities increasingly complex" [1].

- As seen from the above points, compulsory courses in primary education, such as ethics, reading, and mathematics, should include skills that require financial literacy [13]. Based on this, we present recommendations and strategies for improving economic education in the context of Uzbekistan, using examples from the OECD publication "National Strategies for Financial Education" (2015):

- Establishing clear institutional organizations to implement economic education and creating a strong governance mechanism that allows effective collaboration with stakeholders;

- Developing pathways that ensure all members of society have access to economic education;

- Starting economic education as early as possible. Economic education should begin in parallel with compulsory education and continue seamlessly throughout a student's school life.

In the school education system, an economic literacy program should be developed, including its objectives, learning outcomes, content, pedagogical approaches, resources, and assessment procedures. The content of education should focus on enhancing students' knowledge, skills, and competencies.

Economic education can be implemented either as a separate course or integrated with subjects such as ethics, reading, and mathematics. Teachers should have the necessary training and resources for economic education and regularly improve their qualifications in teaching economic subjects. Schools should provide rich economic literacy resources that are engaging for students and accessible to both teachers and students. The scope of research on children's and adults' economic education should be expanded [8].

In conclusion, training highly qualified educators focused on pedagogical activities, as well as improving the methodological preparation of future elementary school teachers, has become one of the essential conditions for the development of modern society. This process is crucial for enhancing the quality of education, developing students' knowledge and skills, and fully realizing their personal and intellectual potential.

REFERENCES

1. APEC Project of Education on Financial and Economic Literacy. <https://www.apec.org/docs/default-source/Publications/2014/11/APEC-Guidebook-on-Financial-and-Economic-Literacy-in-Basic-Education>
2. Chen, H. and Volpe, R. P. (1998). An Analysis Of Personal Financial Literacy Among College Students. *Financial Services Review*, 7(2), 107-128.
3. Gerek, S. and Kurt, A.A, (2011). Ekonomi Okuryazarlığı Ölçeğinin Geçerlik ve Güvenirlik Çalışması. *Uludağ Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 30(1), 59-73.
4. Gratton-L., C. and Gill, A. (2009). A Study of High School Economic Literacy in Orange County California. *Eastern Economic Journal*, 35, 433-451.
5. Japelli, T. (2010). Economic Literacy: An International Comparison. *The Economic Journal*, 120, F429-F451
6. Lusardi, A.M. and Tufano, P. (2009). Debt Literacy, Financial Experiences, and Overindebtedness. NBER Working Paper. no: 14808.
7. Merwe, E. V.D (2012). Economic Literacy As A Factor Affecting Allocative Efficiency. Master of Science In Agricultural Economics. University of The Free State Bloemfontein
8. OECD. (2015). National strategies for financial education. OECD Publishing. https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/national-strategies-for-financial-education-oecd-infe-policy-handbook_a8916d0e-en.html
9. Parkison, K. and Sorgman, M. (1998). Enhancing Economic Literacy of Classroom Teachers. *IAER*, 4(4), 418-427
10. Walstad, W. B. and Soper, J. C. (1988). A Report Card On The Economic Literacy of U.S. High School Students. *The American Economic Review*, 78(2), 251-256
11. Walstad, W. B., Rebeck, K. and Butters, R. B (2013). The Test of Economic Literacy: Development and Results. *The Journal of Economic Education*, 44(3), 298-309.

12. Артамонова М.А. Формирование экономической компетентности будущих педагогов. Маг. дисс. Тольятти 2020.
13. Чиранова О.И. Подготовка будущего учителя к реализации эстетического потенциала начального курса математики. дис. канд. пед. наук. Нижний Новгород 2006.